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Research Article

**VALIDATED STABILITY INDICATING RP – HPLC METHOD
FOR SIMULTANEOUS ESTIMATION OF FURAZOLIDINE
AND METRONIDAZOLE IN COMBINED PHARMACEUTICAL
DOSAGE FORMS****Mrs.Priyanka.K*,Mr.MD.Yakub Pasha,Mr.Bhaskar,Mrs.K.Srivani, Sameena Begum**Smt Sarojini Ramulamma College of Pharmacy,Seshadri Nagar,Mahabub Nagar-
509001,Telangana, India.**Abstract:**

A reverse phase high performance liquid chromatography method was developed for the simultaneous estimation of diloxanide furoate and metronidazole in formulation. The separation was achieved by octadecyl C8 column and a mixture of methanol: acetonitrile: 0.05M phosphate buffer at pH 4.0 (45:25:30 v/v) as eluent, at a flow rate of 1 ml/min. detection was carried out at 277 nm. Quantitation was done by external standard method. The retention time of metronidazole and diloxanide furoate was found to be 3.28 and 6.42 min, respectively. The method has validated for linearity, accuracy and precision. Linearity of metronidazole and diloxanide furoate were in the range of 5-50 µg/ml for both the drugs The mean recoveries obtained for metronidazole and diloxanide furoate were 100.01% and 99.71%, respectively. The developed method was found to be accurate, precise, selective and rapid for the simultaneous estimation of metronidazole and diloxanide furoate in tablet. Key- words: RP-HPLC, metronidazole, diloxanide furoate, simultaneous estimation

Corresponding Author:**Priyanka.K,**Smt Sarojini Ramulamma College of Pharmacy,
Seshadri Nagar,Mahabub Nagar-509001,Telangana, India.

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1.1. INTRODUCTION TO ANALYTICAL CHEMISTRY^{1,2,3}

Analytical chemistry is often described as the area of chemistry responsible for characterizing the composition of matter, both qualitatively (what is present) and quantitatively (how much is present). Analytical chemistry is not a separate branch of chemistry, but simply the application of chemical knowledge.

PHARMACEUTICAL ANALYSIS

Pharmaceutical Analysis is the branch of chemistry involved in separating, identifying and determining the relative amounts of the components making up a sample of matter. It is mainly involved in the qualitative identification or detection of compounds and quantitative measurements of the substances present in bulk and pharmaceutical preparation.

The technique employed in quantitative analysis is based upon the quantitative performance of suitable chemical reactions and either measuring the amount of reagent needed to complete the reaction, or ascertaining the amount of reaction product obtained.

Quality is important in every product or service but it is vital in medicine as it involves life. Unlike ordinary consumer goods there can be no "second quality" in drugs. Quality control is a concept, which strives to produce a perfect product by series of measures designed to prevent and eliminate errors at different stages of production.

Physico-chemical methods are used to study the physical phenomenon that occurs as a result of chemical reactions. Among the Physico-chemical methods, the most important are optical

(Refractometry, Polarimetry, Emission, Fluorescence methods of analysis, Photometry including Photocolorimetry and Spectrophotometry covering UV-Visible and IR regions and Nephelometry or Turbidimetry) and chromatographic (Column, Paper, TLC, GLC, HPLC) methods. Methods such as Nuclear Magnetic Resonance and Para Magnetic Resonance are becoming more and more popular. The combination of Mass Spectroscopy with Gas Chromatography and Liquid Chromatography are the most powerful tools available. The chemical methods include the gravimetric and volumetric procedures which are based on complex formation; acid-base, precipitation and redox reactions. Titrations in non-aqueous media and complexometry have also been used in pharmaceutical analysis.

The number of new drugs is constantly growing. This requires new methods for controlling their quality. Modern pharmaceutical analysis must need the following requirements.

1. The analysis should take a minimal time.
2. The accuracy of the analysis should meet the demands of pharmacopeia
3. The analysis should be economical.
4. The selected method should be precise and selective.

These requirements are met by the Physico-chemical methods of analysis, a merit of which is their universal nature that can be employed for analyzing organic compounds with a diverse structure. Of them, Visible Spectrophotometry is generally preferred especially by small scale industries as the cost of the equipment is less and the maintenance problems are minimal.

Table.No.1.1 Analytical techniques and principal applications

Technique	Basis	Principal applications
Gravimetry	Weight of pure analyte or compound of known as stoichiometry	Quantitative for major or minor components
Titrimetry	Volume of standard reagent solution reacting with the analyte	Quantitative for major or minor Component
Atomic molecular spectrometry	Wavelength and intensity of electromagnetic radiation emitted/ absorbed by the analyte	Qualitative, quantitative or structural or for major down to trace level components
Mass spectrometry	Mass of analyte or fragments of it	Qualitative or structural for major down to trace level components isotope ratios
Chromatography and electrophoresis	Various physicochemical properties of separated analytes	Qualitative and quantitative separations of mixtures at major to trace levels
Thermal analysis	Chemical/physical changes in the	Characterization of single

	analyte when heated or cooled	or mixed major/minor compounds
Electrochemical analysis	Electrical properties of the analyte in solution	Qualitative and quantitative for major to trace level components
Radiochemical analysis	Characteristic ionizing nuclear radiation emitted by the analyte	Qualitative and quantitative at major to trace levels

Table.No.1.2 Spectrometric Techniques and Principal Applications

Technique	Basis	Principal applications
Plasma emission spectrometry	Atomic emission after excitation in high temperature gas plasma	Atomic emission after excitation in high temperature gas plasma
Flame emission spectrometry	Atomic emission after flame excitation	Determination of alkali and alkaline earth metals
Atomic absorption spectrometry	Atomic absorption after atomization by flame or electro thermal means	Determination of trace metals and some nonmetals
Atomic fluorescence spectrometry	Atomic fluorescence emission after flame excitation	Determination of mercury and hydrides of nonmetals at trace levels
X-ray emission spectrometry	Atomic or atomic fluorescence emission after excitation by electrons or radiation	Determination of major and minor elemental components of metallurgical and geological samples
γ - spectrometry	γ -ray emission after nuclear excitation	Monitoring of radioactive elements in environmental samples
Ultraviolet/visible spectrometry	Electronic molecular absorption in solution	Quantitative determination of unsaturated organic
Infrared spectrometry	Vibrational molecular absorption	Identification of organic compounds
Nuclear magnetic resonance spectrometry	Nuclear absorption (change of spin states)	Identification and structural analysis of organic compounds
Mass spectrometry	Ionization and fragmentation of molecules	Identification and structural analysis of organic compounds

Table.No.1.3 Separation techniques and principal applications

Technique	Basis	Principal applications
Thin-layer chromatography	Differential rates of migration of analytes through a stationary phase by movement of a liquid or gaseous mobile phase	Qualitative analysis of mixtures
Gas chromatography	-Do-	Quantitative and qualitative determination of volatile compounds
High-performance liquid chromatography	-Do-	Quantitative and qualitative determination of nonvolatile compounds
Electrophoresis	Differential rates of migration of analytes through a buffered medium	Quantitative and qualitative determination of ionic compounds

1.3 INTRODUCTION TO CHROMATOGRAPHY

Chromatography is a general term applied to a wide variety of separation techniques based on the sample partitioning between a moving phase, which can be a gas, liquid, or supercritical fluid, and a stationary phase, which may be either a liquid or a solid.

Chromatographic separations are based on a forced transport of the liquid (mobile phase) carrying the analyte mixture through the porous media (stationary phase) and the differences in the interactions at analytes with the surface of this porous media resulting in different migration times for a mixture components^[1].

In the above definitions the presence of two different phases is stated and consequently there is an interface between them. One of these phases provides the analyte transport and is usually referred to as the mobile phase, and the other phase is immobile and is typically referred to as the stationary phase.

A mixture of components, usually called analytes, are dispersed in the mobile phase at the molecular level allowing for their uniform transport and interactions with the mobile and stationary phases.

High surface area of the interface between mobile and stationary phases is essential for space

discrimination of different components in the mixture. Analyte molecules undergo multiple phase transitions between mobile phase and adsorbent surface. Average residence time of the molecule on the stationary phase surface is dependent on the interaction energy.

For different molecules with very small interaction energy difference the presence of significant surface is critical since the higher the number of phase transitions that analyte molecules undergo while moving through the chromatographic column, the higher the difference in their retention. The nature of the stationary and the mobile phases, together with the mode of the transport through the column, is the basis for the classification of chromatographic methods.

Chromatographic techniques can be classified according to whether the separation takes place on a planar surface or in a column. They can be further subdivided into gas and liquid chromatography, and by the physical form, solid or liquid, of the stationary phase and the nature of the interactions of solutes with it, known as sorption mechanisms.

1.3.1 Types of chromatography

Based upon the nature of stationary and mobile phase and principle of separation chromatography can be of the following types.

Table 1.4 classification of the principle chromatographic techniques:

Technique	Stationary Phase	Mobile Phase	Format	Principle sorption mechanism
Paper chromatography (PC)	Paper (cellulose)	Liquid	Planar	Partition (adsorption, ion-exchange, exclusion)
Thin-layer chromatography (TLC)	Silica, cellulose, ion-exchange resin, controlled porosity solid	Liquid	Planar	Adsorption (partition, ion-exchange, exclusion)
Gas chromatography (GC)				
Gas-liquid chromatography (GLC)	Liquid	Gas	Column	Partition
Gas-solid chromatography (GSC)	Solid	Gas	Column	Adsorption
Liquid chromatography (LC)				
High performance liquid chromatography (HPLC)	Solid or bonded-phase	Liquid	Column	Modified partition (adsorption)
Size-exclusion chromatography (SEC)	Controlled porosity solid	Liquid	Column	Exclusion
Ion-exchange chromatography (IEC), Ion chromatography (IC)	Ion-exchange resin or bonded-phase	Liquid	Column	Ion-exchange
Chiral chromatography (CC)	Solid chiral selector	Liquid	Column	Selective adsorption

1.4 HIGH PERFORMANCE LIQUID CHROMATOGRAPHY (HPLC) ⁴

The acronym *HPLC*, coined by the Late Prof. Csaba Horvath for his 1970 Pittconpaper, originally indicated the fact that high pressure was used to generate the flow required for liquid chromatography in packed columns. In the beginning, pumps only had a pressure capability of 500 psi [35 bars]. This was called *high pressure liquid chromatography*, or HPLC. The early 1970s saw a tremendous leap in technology. These new HPLC instruments could develop up to 6,000 psi [400 bars] of pressure, and incorporated improved injectors, detectors, and columns. With continued advances in performance during this time [smaller particles, even higher pressure], the acronym HPLC remained the same, but the name was changed to high performance liquid chromatography.

High Performance Liquid Chromatography is now one of the most powerful tools in analytical chemistry. It has the ability to separate, identify, and quantitative the compounds that are present in any sample that can be dissolved in a liquid. Today, compounds in trace concentrations as low as *parts per trillion* may easily be identified. HPLC can be, and has been, applied to just about any sample, such as pharmaceuticals, food, nutraceuticals, cosmetics, environmental matrices, forensic samples, and industrial chemicals.

Normal phase chromatography

Normal phase HPLC (NP-HPLC) was the first kind of HPLC chemistry used, and separate analytes, based on polarity. This method uses a polar stationary phase and a non-polar mobile phase, and is used when the analyte is fairly polar in nature. The polar analyte associates with and is retained by the polar stationary phase. Absorption strengths increase with increase in analyte polarity, and the interaction between the polar analyte and the polar stationary phase increases the elution time. The interaction strength not only depends on the functional groups in the analyte molecule, but also on steric factors and structural isomers is often resolved from one another. Use of more polar solvents in the mobile phase will decrease the retention time of the analyte while more hydrophobic solvents tend to increase retention times. Particularly polar solvents in a mixture tend to deactivate the column by occupying the stationary phase surface.

Fig.No.1.1 Normal-Phase Chromatography

Reversed phase chromatography (RPC)

Reversed phase HPLC (RP-HPLC) consists of a non-polar stationary phase and an aqueous, moderately polar mobile phase. One common stationary phase is silica which has been treated with RMe₂SiCl, where R is a straight chain alkyl group such as C₁₈H₃₇ or C₈H₁₇. The retention time is therefore longer for molecules which are more non-polar in nature, allowing polar molecules to elute more readily. Retention Time (Rt) is increased by the addition of polar solvent to the mobile phase and decreased by the addition of more hydrophobic solvent. The pharmaceutical industry regularly employs RPC to qualify drugs before their release. RPC operates on the principle of hydrophobic interactions, which result from repulsive forces between a polar eluent, the relatively non-polar analyte, and the nonpolar stationary phase. The binding of the analyte to the stationary phase is proportional to the contact surface area around the non-polar segment of the analyte molecule upon association with the ligand in the aqueous eluent. The energy released in this process is proportional to the surface tension of the eluent (water: 73 erg/cm², methanol: 22 erg/cm²) and to the hydrophobic surface of the analyte and the ligand respectively. The retention can be decreased by adding less-polar solvent (MeOH, ACN) into the mobile phase to reduce the surface tension of water. Gradient elution uses this effect by automatically changing the polarity of the mobile phase during the course of the analysis.

Fig.No.1.2. Reversed-Phase Chromatography

1.5 INTRODUCTION TO METHOD DEVELOPMENT

For pharmaceutical manufacturers to achieve commercial production of safe and effective medications requires the generation of a vast amount of reliable data during the development of each product. To ensure that reliable data are generated in compliance with current Good Manufacturing Practices (cGMPs), all analytical activities involved in the process need to follow Good Analytical Practices. Good Analytical Practices can be considered as the culmination of a three-pronged approach to data generation and management: method validation, calibrated instrument, and training. Whereas individual approaches may exhibit considerable diversity, method development often follows the series of steps summarized in Flow chart 1.1

Nature of the sample

Before beginning method development, we need to review what is known about the sample. The goals of the separation should also be defined at this time. The kind of sample related information that can be important is.

1. Number of component present.
2. Chemical structure (functionality) of the compound.
3. Molecular weights of compounds and sample solubility

4. pKa values of compounds.
5. UV spectra of compounds.
6. Concentration range of compounds in sample of interest.

Separation goals

The goals of HPLC separation need to be specified clearly. Some related questions that should be asked at the beginning of the method development include.

Table 1.5 separation goals

Goal	Comment
Resolution	Precise and rugged quantitative analysis requires that resolution be greater than 1.5
Separation time	< 5-10 minutes is desirable for routine procedure (e.g. Dissolution profile)
Quantitation	< 2% RSD for assays
Pump pressure	< 150 Bar is desirable, < 200 bar is usually essential (For UPLC-Waters and RRLC-Agilent these values are 5 fold and 3 fold respectively)
Peak height	Narrow peaks are desirable for large signal/noise ratio
Solvent consumption	Minimum mobile phase use per run is desirable

Sample pretreatment and detection

Sample comes in various forms

1. Solution ready for injection
2. Solution that require dilution, buffering, addition of an internal standard.
3. Solids that must first be dissolved or extracted.
4. Samples requiring pretreatment to remove interferences and to protect the column and the equipment form damage.

Best result are often obtained when the composition of the sample solvent is close to that of the mobile since this minimizes baseline upset and other problems. Some sample require partial separation prior to HPLC analysis because of the need to remove interference, concentrate sample analytes or eliminate "column killer" this means that it is important to know the nature of sample and concentration of various analytes.

For this reason, information on the UV spectra can be as important aid for method development. UV spectra can be found in literature, estimated from the chemical structures of the sample components of

interest, measured directly or obtained during HPLC separation by means of Photodiode-array (PDA) detector. When the UV response of the sample is inadequate, other detectors are available such as fluorescence, electrochemical etc. or the sample can be derivatized for enhanced detection.

1.5.4 Developing the separation

Samples classified as ionic include acids, bases, amphoteric compounds and organic salts. If the sample is neutral, buffer or additives are generally not required in the mobile phase. Acids or bases usually require the addition of a buffer to the mobile phase. For basic or cationic samples, "less acidic" reversed phase columns are recommended and amine additives for the mobile phase may be beneficial.

Using this condition, the first exploratory run is carried out and then improved systematically.. Alternatively, the sample may be strongly retained with 100% acetonitrile as mobile phase, suggesting the use of non aqueous reversed phase chromatography or normal phase HPLC. Flow chart 1.2 summarizes the appropriate experimental condition for initial separation of regular and special samples.

INTRODUCTION TO ANALYTICAL METHOD VALIDATION:

Once an analytical method is developed for its intended use, it must be validated. The extent of validation evolves with the drug development phase. Usually, a limited validation is carried out to support an Investigational New Drug (IND) application and a more extensive validation for New Drug Application (NDA) and Marketing Authorization Application (MAA). Typical parameters recommended by FDA, USP, and ICH are as follow⁵

- Accuracy (Recovery)
- Precision
 - Method precision (Repeatability)
 - Intermediate precision (Ruggedness)
- Limit of Detection (LOD)
- Limit of Quantification (LOQ)
- Linearity & Range
- Robustness
- Solution stability
- Specificity

Accuracy:

The accuracy of an analytical procedure expresses the closeness of agreement between the value that is accepted either as a conventional true value or as an accepted reference value and the value found⁶. Accuracy should be assessed using a minimum of 9 determinations over a minimum of 3 concentration levels covering the specified range (e.g. 3 concentrations/ 3 replicates each of the total analytical procedure).

Accuracy should be reported as percent recovery by the assay of known added amount of analyte in the sample or as the difference between the mean and the accepted true value together with the confidence intervals. Accuracy was tested (% Recovery and % RSD of individual measurements) by analyzing samples at least in triplicate, at each level (80,100 and 120 % of label claim) is recommended. For each determination fresh samples were prepared and assay value is calculated. Recovery was calculated from regression equation obtained in linearity study. Accuracy was determined from the mean relative error for a set of replicate analysis (i.e. the difference between measured and nominal concentration) for spiked samples.

Precision:

The precision of an analytical procedure expresses the closeness of agreement (degree of scatter) between a series of measurements obtained from multiple sampling of the same homogeneous sample

under the prescribed conditions⁷. The precision is expressed as the relative standard deviation

Precision may be considered at three levels:

- a. Repeatability,
- b. Intermediate precision and
- c. Reproducibility.

Repeatability expresses the precision under the same operating conditions over a short interval of time. Repeatability is also termed **intra assay precision**. Repeatability should be assessed using:

- i. A minimum of 9 determinations covering the specified range for the procedure (e.g. 3 concentrations/ 3 replicates each) or
- ii. A minimum of 6 determinations at 100% of the test concentration.

Intermediate Precision: Intermediate precision expresses with in laboratories variations: different days, different analyst and different equipment

Reproducibility: Reproducibility expresses the precision between laboratories (Collaborative studies are generally used, for standardization of methodology). This is an optional validation parameter that requires demonstration of laboratory to laboratory variation only if multiple laboratories use the same procedure.

Limit of detection

LOD is defined as the Lowest amount of analyte in a sample which can be detected but not necessarily quantified.

- i. **Based on Visual Evaluation:** Visual evaluation may be used for non-instrumental methods but may also be used with instrumental methods. The detection limit is determined by the analysis of samples with known concentrations of analyte and by establishing the minimum level at which the analyte can be reliably detected.
- ii. **Based on Signal-to-Noise:** This approach can only be applied to analytical procedures which exhibit baseline noise. Determination of the signal-to-noise ratio is performed by comparing measured signals from samples with known low concentrations of analyte with those of blank samples and establishing the minimum concentration at which the analyte can be reliably detected. A signal-to-noise ratio between 3 or 2:1 is generally considered acceptable for estimating the detection limit.
- iii. **Based on the Standard Deviation of the Response and the Slope:** The detection limit (DL) may be expressed as:

$DL = 3.3 \sigma/s$; Where σ = the standard deviation of the response

s = the slope of the calibration curve

Limit of quantitation (LOQ):

It is defined as the lowest amount of analyte in a sample that can be determined with acceptable precision and accuracy under the stated experimental conditions. Quantification limit is expressed as the concentration of analyte (e.g- % ppm) in the sample. LOQ is determined by the following methods

i. Based on Visual Evaluation: The quantitation limit is generally determined by the analysis of

samples with known concentrations of analyte and by establishing the minimum level at which the analyte can be quantified with acceptable accuracy and precision.

ii. Based on Signal-to-Noise Approach: This approach can only be applied to analytical procedures that exhibit baseline noise. Determination of the signal-to-noise ratio is performed by comparing measured signals from samples with known low concentrations of analyte with those of blank samples and by establishing the minimum concentration at which the analyte can be reliably quantified. A typical signal-to-noise ratio is 10:1.

MATERIALS AND METHOD:

INSTRUMENTS USED

List of Instruments used

SL.No	Instrument	Model
1	HPLC	WATERS, 2695 separation module. PDA detector. software: Empower
2	UV/VIS spectrophotometer	LABINDIA UV 3000 ⁺ , Software: UV win5
3	pH meter	LAB INDIA
4	Weighing machine	Sartorius
5	Sonicator	Digital ultra sonicator (2500ml)
5	Pipettes and Burettes	Borosilicate
6	Beakers, volumetric flask	Borosilicate

CHEMICALS AND STANDARDS USED:

List of chemicals and standards used

SL.No	Chemical	Brand
1	Metronidazole	Aristo pharmaceuticals
2	Furazolidone	Aristo pharmaceuticals
3	Dependal – M (Metronidazole and Furazolidone)	Glaxosmithkline pharmaceuticals
4	Potassium dihydrogen phosphate buffer	LR grade
5	Water for HPLC	LICHROSOLV (MERCK)
6	Methanol for HPLC	LICHROSOLV (MERCK)
7	Acetonitrile for HPLC	MOLYCHEM
8	Hydrochloric acid	MERCK
9	Hydrogen peroxide	MERCK
10	Sodium hydroxide	MERCK
11	0.45µfilter paper	Millipore HPLC grade

12	Orthophosphoric acid	LR grade
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HPLC METHOD DEVELOPMENT:**Mobile Phase Optimization:**

Initially the mobile phase tried was Phosphate buffer: Methanol: water, Phosphate buffer: Methanol, acetonitrile: Methanol: phosphate buffer with varying proportions. Finally, the mobile phase optimized was acetonitrile: Methanol : phosphate buffer in proportion 10:40:50 v/v respectively.

Wave length selection:

UV spectrum of 10 µg / ml Metronidazole and Furazolidone in diluents (mobile phase composition) was recorded by scanning in the range of 200nm to 400nm. From the UV spectrum wavelength selected as 270. At this wavelength both the drugs show good absorbance.

Optimization of Column:

The method that was performed with column Symmetry C18 (4.6 x 250mm, 5µm, Make: XTerra) was found to be ideal as it gave good peak shape and resolution at 1.0ml/min flow.

Optimized Chromatographic Conditions:

Instrument used : Waters RP-HPLC with auto sampler and PDA detector.

Column : Symmetry C18 (4.6 x 150mm, 5µm, Make XTerra)

Mobile phase : acetonitrile: Methanol : phosphate buffer (10:40:50)

Flow rate : 1ml per min

Wavelength : 270 nm

Temperature : ambient.

Run time : 8mins.

Optimized chromatogram is shown in the **figure 6.1(a)** and blank is shown in the **figure 6.1(b)**. System suitability parameters are shown in **figure 6.2** and the results are shown in **Table 1**

PREPARATION OF BUFFER AND MOBILE PHASE:**5.4.1: Preparation of Potassium Dihydrogen phosphate (0.025M) buffer:**

Potassium Dihydrogen phosphate (0.025M) buffer was prepared by dissolving 1.7 gms of buffer in 250 ml of water and by adjusting the pH to 2.5 with dilute ortho phosphoric acid.

Preparation of mobile phase:

Potassium Dihydrogen phosphate (0.025M) buffer Acetonitrile HPLC and methanol were mixed in the ratio of 50:10:40 respectively and degassed in an ultrasonic water bath for 10 minutes and then filtered through 0.45 µ filter under vacuum filtration.

Diluent Preparation:

The Mobile phase was used as the diluents

5.5: VALIDATION PARAMETERS:**5.5.1: Method Precision:****5.5.1.1: Preparation of Standard Solution:**

Accurately weighed amounts of 10mg Furazolidone and 30mg of Metronidazole were taken to a 10 ml cleaned and dried volumetric flasks. They were then diluted with 7ml of diluent and were sonicated. The volumes were made to 10 ml with the same solvent. They were marked and labeled as Stock solutions. Further, an amount of 0.1 ml of Furazolidone and 0.3ml of Metronidazole were pipetted from the above stock solutions into a 10ml volumetric flask and diluted up to the mark with diluents to get 10 µg/ml of Furazolidone and 30 µg/ml of Metronidazole.

5.5.1.2 Preparation of Sample Solution:

57.8mg of Metronidazole and Furazolidone tablet powder i.e marketed product (equivalent to 10mg) was accurately weighed and transferred into 10 ml cleaned and dried volumetric flask. This was then diluted with 7ml of diluent and was sonicated. The volume was made to 10 ml with the same solvent. This was marked and labeled as Stock solution. Further, 0.1mg from the above stock solution was pipette into a 10ml volumetric flask and diluted up to the mark with diluents to get 30 µg/ml of Metronidazole and 10 µg/ml of Furazolidone.

The standard and sample solutions of 30 µg/ml of Metronidazole and 10 µg/ml of Furazolidone were injected for five times and the peak areas were recorded as shown in **Figure 6.4.1 (a) - 6.4.1 (e)**

The mean and percentage relative standard deviations were calculated from the peak areas and shown in the **Table 6.3 and 6.4.**

5.5.2: Intermediate Precision/Ruggedness:

30 µg/ml of Metronidazole and 10 µg/ml of Furazolidone of the above sample solution was injected for five times in five different days and peak areas were recorded.

Accuracy:

For accuracy determination, three different concentrations were prepared separately i.e. 50%, 100% and 150% for the analyte and chromatograms are recorded for the same.

Preparation Sample solutions:**Preparation of 50% solution (45µg/ml of Metronidazole and 15µg/ml of Furazolidone):**

57.8mg of Metronidazole and Furazolidone tablet powder i.e marketed product (equivalent to 10mg) was accurately weighed and transferred into 10 ml cleaned and dried volumetric flask. This was then diluted with 7ml of diluent and was sonicated. The volume was made to 10 ml with the same solvent. This was marked and labeled as Stock solution. Further, 0.15ml from the above stock solution into a 10ml volumetric flask and diluted up to the mark

with diluents to get 45 µg/ml of Metronidazole and 15 µg/ml of Furazolidone.

Preparation of 100% solution (90µg/ml of Metronidazole and 30µg/ml of Furazolidone):

57.8mg of Metronidazole and Furazolidone tablet powder i.e marketed product (equivalent to 10mg) was accurately weighed and transferred into 10 ml cleaned and dried volumetric flask. This was then diluted with 7ml of diluent and was sonicated. The volume was made to 10 ml with the same solvent. This was marked and labeled as Stock solution. Further, 0.3ml from the above stock solution into a 10ml volumetric flask and diluted up to the mark with diluents to get 90µg/ml of Metronidazole and 30µg/ml of Furazolidone.

Preparation of 150% solution (135µg/ml of Metronidazole and 45µg/ml of Furazolidone):

57.8mg of Metronidazole and Furazolidone tablet powder i.e marketed product (equivalent to 10mg) was accurately weighed and transferred into 10 ml cleaned and dried volumetric flask. This was then diluted with 7ml of diluent and was sonicated. The volume was made to 10 ml with the same solvent. This was marked and labeled as Stock solution. Further, 0.45ml from the above stock solution into a 10ml volumetric flask and diluted up to the mark with diluents to get 135µg/ml of Metronidazole and 45µg/ml of Furazolidone.

These solutions were filtered through 0.45µm membrane and then each concentration; three replicate injections were made under the optimized conditions. The chromatograms were recorded and peak responses were measured. The chromatograms are shown in figure 6.4.3(a)-6.4.3(c) Results are shown in the table-6.7,6.8

5.5.4: Linearity:

5.5.4.1: Preparation of sample stock solution:

57.8mg of Metronidazole and Furazolidone tablet powder i.e marketed product (equivalent to 10mg) was accurately weighed and transferred into 10 ml cleaned and dried volumetric flask. This was then diluted with 7ml of diluent and was sonicated. The volume was made to 10 ml with the same solvent. This was marked and labeled as Stock solution.

Preparation of Level – I (30 µg/ml of Metronidazole & 10 µg/ml of Furazolidone)

0.1ml of stock solution had taken in 10ml of volumetric flask diluted up to the mark with diluent.

Preparation of Level – II (60 µg/ml of Metronidazole & 20 µg/ml of Furazolidone)

0.2ml of stock solution had taken in 10ml of volumetric flask diluted up to the mark with diluent.

Preparation of Level – III (90 µg/ml of Metronidazole & 30 µg/ml of Furazolidone)

0.3ml of stock solution had taken in 10ml of volumetric flask diluted up to the mark with diluent.

Preparation of Level – IV (120 µg/ml of Metronidazole & 40 µg/ml of Furazolidone)

0.4ml of stock solution had taken in 10ml of volumetric flask diluted up to the mark with diluent.

Preparation of Level – V (150 µg/ml of Metronidazole & 50µg/ml of Furazolidone)

0.5ml of stock solution had taken in 10ml of volumetric flask diluted up to the mark with diluent.

10µl of each 30 µg/ml of Metronidazole & 10 µg/ml of Furazolidone ; 60 µg/ml of Metronidazole & 20 µg/ml of Furazolidone, 90 µg/ml of Metronidazole & 30 µg/ml of Furazolidone, 120 µg/ml of Metronidazole & 40 µg/ml of Furazolidone, 150 µg/ml of Metronidazole & 50µg/ml of Furazolidone were injected in triplicate and the peak responses were recorded.

The chromatograms were recorded as shown in Figure 6.4.4 (a) – 6.4.4 (e) and results are shown in Table- 6.9 and 6.10.

5.5.5: Limit of Detection (for Metronidazole):

LOD is calculated based on the standard deviation of the response (SD) and the slope of the calibration curve (S) at levels approximating the LOD according to the formula. The standard deviation of the response can be determined based on the standard deviation of y-intercepts of regression lines.

$$LOD = 3.3(SD/S).$$

Where SD = standard deviation

S = slope

Results are shown in table 6.11

5.5.6: Limit of Quantification:

LOQ calculation is based on the standard deviation of the response (SD) and the slope of the calibration curve (S) according to the formula:. Again, the standard deviation of the response can be determined based on the standard deviation of y-intercepts of regression lines.

$$LOQ = 10(SD/S)$$

Where SD = standard deviation

S = slope

Results are shown in table 6.12

5.5.7: Robustness:

The analysis was performed in different conditions to find the variability of test results. The following conditions were checked for variation of results. .

Preparation of sample solution (90µg/ml of Metronidazole 30 µg/ml of Furazolidone)

57.8mg of Metronidazole and Furazolidone tablet powder i.e marketed product (equivalent to 10mg) was accurately weighed and transferred into 10 ml cleaned and dried volumetric flask. This was then diluted with 7ml of diluent and was sonicated. The volume was made to 10 ml with the same solvent. This was marked and labeled as Stock solution. 0.3ml

of stock solution was taken in 10ml of volumetric flask and diluted up to the mark with diluent.

Variation of flow:

The sample was analyzed at 0.9 ml/min and 1.1 ml/min instead of 1.0 ml/min, remaining conditions are same. 10 μ l of the above sample was injected thrice and chromatograms were recorded.

Variation of mobile phase organic composition:

The sample was analyzed by variation of mobile phase i.e. phosphate buffer: acetonitrile and methanol were taken in the ratio 40: 10: 50 and 60:10:30 instead of 50:10:40. Remaining conditions were same. 10 μ l of the above sample was injected thrice and chromatograms were recorded.

The chromatograms were recorded as shown in **Figure 6.4.7 (a) - 6.4.7 (d)** and results are shown in **Table 6.13 and 6.14.**

Specificity

Specificity is the ability to assess unequivocally the analyte in the presence of components which may be expected to be present. Typically these might include impurities, degradants, matrix, etc. assay was performed by sample solution and mobile phase.

Preparation of sample solution

57.8mg of Metronidazole and Furazolidone tablet powder i.e marketed product (equivalent to 10mg) was accurately weighed and transferred into 10 ml cleaned and dried volumetric flask. This was then diluted with 7ml of diluent and was sonicated. The volume was made to 10 ml with the same solvent. This was marked and labeled as Stock solution. Further, 0.1mg from the above stock solution was pipette into a 10ml volumetric flask and diluted up to the mark with diluents to get 30 μ g/ml of Metronidazole and 10 μ g/ml of Furazolidone.

Blank and the above sample was injected and chromatograms were recorded.

The chromatograms were recorded as shown in **Figure 6.4.8 (a) - 6.3.9 (d)**

5.5.9 Range

Based on precision, linearity and accuracy data it can be concluded that the assay method is precise, linear and accurate in the range of 10 μ g-60 μ g and 30 μ g-150 μ g of Furazolidone and Metronidazole respectively.

STABILITY STUDIES:

Preparation of 0.1N HCl

8.1774 ml of 37.5% concentrated HCl is taken into 1L volumetric flask. the volume is made upto the mark using distilled water.

Preparation of 0.1N NaOH

4gms of NaOH is taken in 1L of volumetric flask. NaOH is dissolved by adding distilled water in different volumes. Finally the volume is made upto the mark by water.

5.6.1: Acid degradation:

57.8mg of Metronidazole and Furazolidone tablet powder i.e marketed product (equivalent to 10mg) was accurately weighed and transferred into 10 ml cleaned and dried volumetric flask. 3 ml of 0.1N HCl was added and sonicated for 10minutes and was kept in darkness for 12 hours then refluxed under heat at 60 degrees in a heating mantle for 1 hour. The sample solution was neutralized using 0.1N NaOH and diluted up to the mark with Stock solution. Further 0.1 ml of the above stock solution was pipetted into a 10ml volumetric flask and diluted up to the mark with diluent. Mixed well and filtered through 0.45 μ m filter.

5.6.2: Base Degradation:

57.8mg of Metronidazole and Furazolidone tablet powder i.e marketed product (equivalent to 10mg) was accurately weighed and transferred into 10 ml cleaned and dried volumetric flask. 3 ml of 0.1N NaOH was added and sonicated for 10minutes and was kept in darkness for 12 hours then refluxed under heat at 60 degrees in a heating mantle for 1 hour. The sample solution was neutralized using 0.1N HCl and diluted up to the mark with Stock solution.

Further 0.1 ml of the above stock solution was pipetted into a 10ml volumetric flask and diluted up to the mark with diluent. Mixed well and filtered through 0.45 μ m filter Chromatograms were shown in **figure 6.5.2**

5.6.3: Thermal Degradation:-

57.8mg of Metronidazole and Furazolidone tablet powder i.e marketed product (equivalent to 10mg) was accurately weighed and transferred into 10 ml cleaned and dried volumetric flask. This was kept in an oven under heat at 105 degrees for 12 hours. This was diluted upto the mark using stock solution. Further 0.1 ml was pipetted out of the above stock solution into a 10ml volumetric flask and diluted up to the mark with diluents(M.P). Mixed well and filtered through 0.45 μ m filter.

5.6.4: Peroxide Degradation:-

57.8 mg of Metronidazole and Furazolidone(equivalent to 10mg) was accurately weighed and transferred into a 10ml volumetric flask. 3ml of 3% Hydrogen Peroxide (H₂O₂) was added and sonicated for 10 minutes and kept in darkness for 12 hours and refluxed under heat at 60 degrees in a heating mantle for 1 hour.

Further 0.1 ml of the above stock solution was pipetted out into a 10ml volumetric flask and diluted up to the mark with diluent. Mixed well and filtered through 0.45 μ m filter. Chromatogram is shown in **figure 6.5.4**

5.6.5 Photo Stability

57.8 mg of Metronidazole and Furazolidone(equivalent to 10mg) was accurately weighed and transferred into a 10ml volumetric flask

and exposed to sunlight for 2 days and diluted upto the mark with stock solution.

0.1ml of above solution was pipetted to 10ml volumetric flask and made upto the mark with diluents. Mixed well and filtered through 0.45 μ m filter.

Chromatogram is shown in **fig 6.5.5**

6. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

The present investigation reported in the thesis was aimed to develop and validate a new method for the simultaneous estimation of Metronidazole and Furazolidone by RP-HPLC method and to perform forced degradation studies. Literature reveals that there are no analytical methods reported for the simultaneous estimation Metronidazole and

Furazolidone by RPHPLC method. Hence, it was felt that, there is a need of new validated analytical method development and stability studies for the simultaneous estimation of Metronidazole and Furazolidone in pharmaceutical dosage form.

6.1. Detection of wavelength by UV

The detection wavelength was selected by dissolving the drug in mobile phase to get a concentration of 10 μ g/ml for individual and mixed standards. The resulting solution was scanned in U.V range from 200-400nm. The overlay spectrum of Metronidazole and Furazolidone was obtained and the isobestic point of Metronidazole and Furazolidone showed absorbance's maxima at 243nm. The spectrums are shown in Fig.6.1.1

6.1.1 Spectrum showing overlapping spectrum of Metronidazole and Furazolidone

Sl.no	Wavelength	Max absorbance	Description
1	270	0.740	Metronidazole and Furazolidone

6.1.2 Spectrum showing the wavelength of Metronidazole

Sl.no	Wavelength	Max absorbance	Description
1	296	0.952	Metronidazole

6.1.3 Spectrum showing wavelength of Furazolidone

Sl.no	Wavelength	Max absorbance	Description
1	250	1.056	Furazolidone

The chromatographic method development for the simultaneous estimation of Metronidazole and Furazolidone was optimized by several trials for various parameters as different column, flow rate and mobile phase. Finally the following chromatographic method was selected for the separation and quantification of Metronidazole and Furazolidone in API and pharmaceutical dosage form by RP-HPLC method.

6.2 Optimized chromatogram is obtained by following conditions:

Trial 1:

Instrument used : Waters RP-HPLC with auto sampler and PDA detector.
 Column : Symmetry C18 (250mm x 4.6, 5 μ m, Make: XTerra)
 Mobile phase : Phosphate buffer: Methanol: water (10:70:20)
 Flow rate : 1ml per min

Wavelength : 270 nm
 Temperature : ambient.
 Run time : 8 min.

6.2a Trial chromatogram for Metronidazole and Furazolidone Auto-Scaled Chromatogram

s.no	name	RT	Area	height	USP resolution	USP tailing	USP plate count
1	Metronidazole	3.181	63551	48773			1593
2	Furazolidone	3.430	58965	6671			

Observation:

From the above chromatogram it was observed that Metronidazole and Furazolidone peaks were found but had no symmetry and no resolution.

Trial 2:

Instrument used : Waters RP-HPLC with auto sampler and PDA detector.
 Column : Symmetry C18 (4.6 x 250mm, 5 μ m, Make: XTerra)
 Mobile phase : Phosphate buffer : Methanol (50:50)
 Flow rate : 1ml per min
 Wavelength : 270 nm
 Temperature : ambient.
 Run time : 8mins.

6.2b Trial chromatogram for Metronidazole and Furazolidone Auto-Scaled Chromatogram

s.no	name	RT	Area	height	USP resolution	USP tailing	USP plate count
1	Metronidazole	3.552	301604	31122		1.40	3161
2	Furazolidone	3.430	58965	6671	1.64	1.43	3284

Observation:

From the above chromatogram it was observed that the Metronidazole and Furazolidone peaks are well formed but had no acceptable resolution.

Trial 3:

Instrument used : Waters RP-HPLC with auto sampler and PDA detector.

Column : Symmetry C18 (4.6 x 150mm, 5 μ m, Make XTerra)

Mobile phase : acetonitrile: Methanol : phosphate buffer (10:30:60)

Flow rate : 1ml per min

Wavelength : 270 nm

Temperature : ambient.

Run time : 8mins.

Figure no 6.2c chromatogram for Metronidazole and Furazolidone

s.no	Name	RT	Area	height	USP resolution	USP tailing	USP plate count
1	Metronidazole	3.787	315071	31901		1.29	3567
2	Furazolidone	5.175	354441	28453	4.72	1.46	4310

From the above chromatogram it was observed that the Metronidazole and Furazolidone peaks are well separated. But elution time is more.

Figure no 6.2d chromatogram for Metronidazole and Furazolidone

s.no	name	RT	Area	height	USP resolution	USP tailing	USP plate count
1	Metronidazole	3.440	791096	76796		1.6	2329
2	Furazolidone	4.136	115578	10468	2.2	1.5	2830

Observation

From the above chromatogram it was observed that the Metronidazole and Furazolidone peaks are well separated and elution was fast.

Optimized Chromatographic Conditions:

Instrument used : Waters RP-HPLC with auto sampler and PDA detector.

Column : Symmetry C18 (4.6 x 150mm, 5 μ m, Make XTerra)

Mobile phase : acetonitrile: Methanol : phosphate buffer (10:40:50)

Flow rate : 1ml per min

Wavelength : 270 nm

Temperature : ambient.

Run time : 8mins.

Blank:

Figure 6.2e chromatogram for blank

From the above chromatogram it was observed that there are no interferences

6.3: SYSTEM SUITABILITY:

s.no	name	RT	Area	height	USP resolution	USP tailing	USP plate count
1	Metronidazole	3.440	791096	76796		1.6	2329
2	Furazolidone	4.136	115578	10468	2.2	1.5	2830

Acceptance criteria:

- Resolution between two drugs must be not less than 2
- Theoretical plates must be not less than 2000
- Tailing factor must be not less than 0.9 and not more than 2.
- It was found from above data that all the system suitability parameters for developed method were within the limit.

6.3.1 Assay calculation for Metronidazole and Furazolidone

The assay study was performed for the Metronidazole and Furazolidone. Each three injections of sample and standard were injected into chromatographic system. The chromatograms are shown figures and results are tabulated in Table.No.

6.3.1a chromatogram showing assay sample injection 1**6.3.1b chromatogram showing assay sample injection 2**

6.3.1c chromatogram showing assay sample injection 3

Table:6.1 results of assay sample of Metronidazole and Furazolidone

S.No	Name	RT	Area ($\mu\text{V sec}$)	Height (μV)	USP resolution	USP tailing	USP plate count
1	Metronidazole	3.440	791096	76796		1.6	2329.0
2	Metronidazole	3.435	797904	75899		1.6	2290.7
3	Metronidazole	3.439	793237	79144		1.6	2588.7
	Mean		792079			1.6	2402.8
	STD		1081.1				
	%RSD		0.1				
1	Furazolidone	4.136	115578	10468	2.2	1.5	2830.0
2	Furazolidone	4.128	115896	10334	2.2	1.5	2713.0
3	Furazolidone	4.129	117796	10826	2.3	1.5	3025.8
	Mean		116423		2.2	1.5	2856.3
	STD		1199.3				
	%RSD		1.0				

6.3.1d.Chromatogram showing assay of standard injection -

6.1.3e. Chromatogram showing assay of standard injection -2

6.1.3f. Chromatogram showing assay of standard injection -3

Table:6.2 Results of assay standard of Metronidazole and Furazolidone

S.No	Name	RT	Area (μV sec)	Height (μV)	USP resolution	USP tailing	USP plate count
1	Metronidazole	3.432	587965	58359		1.5	2627.8
2	Metronidazole	3.432	589824	59486		1.6	2633
3	Metronidazole	3.423	591073	58594		1.5	2555.3
	Mean		589620			1.5	2605.5
	STD		1564				
	%RSD		0.3				
1	Furazolidone	4.115	121409	11134	2.3	1.5	3019.5
2	Furazolidone	4.106	122062	10908	2.3	1.5	2915.5
3	Furazolidone	4.086	124833	11081	2.3	1.5	2761.7
	Mean		122767		2.3	1.5	2898
	STD		1817.7				
	%RSD		1.5				

Observation: the results were found to be within the limits.

6.4: VALIDATION PARAMETERS:

6.4.1: Precision:

The standard solution was injected for five times and area was measured for all the five injections in HPLC. The %RSD for the area of five replicate injections was found to be within the specified limits.

Figure no 6.4.1 (a) chromatogram for sample injection-1

Figure no 6.4.1 (b) chromatogram for sample injection-2

Figure no 6.4.1 (c) chromatogram for sample injection-3

Figure no 6.4.1 (d) chromatogram for sample injection-4

Figure no 6.4.1 (e) chromatogram for sample injection-5

Table 6.3: Results of system precision for Metronidazole:

S.No	Peak name	RT	Area	Height
1	Metronidazole	3.490	592498	55999
2	Metronidazole	3.439	593161	57310
3	Metronidazole	3.439	593999	58227
4	Metronidazole	3.444	594213	57191
5	Metronidazole	3.439	594440	57217
Mean			593662.2	
STD			810.6	
% RSD			0.1	

Table 6.4: Results of system precision for Furazolidone:

S.No	Peak name	RT	area	height
1	Furazolidone	4.197	119688	10298
2	Furazolidone	4.156	121862	10854
3	Furazolidone	4.157	1222928	10641
4	Furazolidone	4.139	123018	10690
5	Furazolidone	4.144	123680	10678
Mean			122235.3	
STD			1565.7	
% RSD			1.3	

Observation: the %RSD was found to be not more than 2. Hence the experiment is precise.

6.4.2. Intermediate Precision (ruggedness)

There was no significant change in assay content and system suitability parameters at different conditions of ruggedness like day to day and system to system variation.

Figure no 6.4.2 (a) chromatogram for standard injection -1**Figure no 6.4.2(b) chromatogram for standard injection-2**

Figure no 6.4.2 (c) chromatogram for standard injection-3

Figure no 6.4.2 (d) chromatogram for standard injection-4

Figure no 6.4.2 (e) chromatogram for standard injection-5

Table6.5: Results of Intermediate precision for Metronidazole:

S.No	Peak name	RT	Area	Height
1	Metronidazole	3.424	587315	54154
2	Metronidazole	3.423	587506	53403
3	Metronidazole	3.424	587876	55122
4	Metronidazole	3.412	588543	53992
5	Metronidazole	3.429	591288	55420
Mean			588505.7	
STD			1624	
% RSD			0.3	

Table 6.6 Results of Intermediate precision for Furazolidone

S.No	Peak name	RT	Area	Height
1	Furazolidone	4.115	120577	10307
2	Furazolidone	4.088	121419	10146
3	Furazolidone	4.110	122484	10168
4	Furazolidone	4.126	122730	10385
5	Furazolidone	4.103	123630	10032
Mean			122167.9	
STD			1188.2	
% RSD			1.0	

Acceptance criteria:

- %RSD of five different sample solutions should not more than 2
- The %RSD obtained is within the limit, hence the method is rugged.

6.4.3: Accuracy:

Sample solutions at different concentrations (50%, 100%, and 150%) were prepared and the % recovery was calculated.

1. For 50%:**Figure no 6.4.3 (1a) chromatogram for sample concentration-50%****Figure no 6.4.3 (1c) chromatogram for sample concentration-50%**

2. For 100%:

Figure no 6.4.3 (2a) chromatogram for sample concentration-100%

Figure no 6.4.3 (2b) chromatogram for sample concentration-100%

Figure no 6.4.3 (2c) chromatogram for sample concentration-100%

3. For 150%:

Figure no 6.4.3 (3a) chromatogram for sample concentration-150%

Figure no 6.4.3 (3b) chromatogram for sample concentration-150%

Figure no 6.4.3 (3c) chromatogram for sample concentration-150%

Table-6.7 Accuracy (recovery) data for Metronidazole:

%concentration	area	Amount present (mg)	Amount found (mg)	% recovery
50	914309	135	134.0393	99.288
100	1208749	180	181.9468	101.0816
150	1467481	225	224.0444	99.5753
Mean % recovery				99.9817

Table-6.8 Accuracy (recovery) data for Furazolidone:

%concentration	area	Amount present (mg)	Amount found (mg)	% recovery
50	190466.8	45	43.9997	97.77725
100	251582.5	60	59.1536	98.58935
150	311479.9	75	74.0054	98.6739
Mean %recovery				98.34679

Acceptance Criteria:

- The percentage recovery was found to be within the limit (98-102%).

The results obtained for recovery at 50%, 100%, 150% are within the limits for both metronidazole and furazolidone Hence method is accurate.

6.4.4 Linearity:

The linearity range was found to lie from 30 μ g/ml to 150 μ g/ml of Metronidazole, 10 μ g/ml to 50 μ g/ml of Furazolidone and chromatograms are shown below.

Figure no 6.4.4 (a) chromatogram for linearity concentration-30 μ g/ml of Metronidazole & 10 μ g/ml of Furazolidone

Figure no 6.4.4 (b) chromatogram for linearity concentration-60 µg/ml of Metronidazole & 20µg/ml of Furazolidone

Figure no 6.4.4 (c) chromatogram for linearity concentration--90 µg/ml of Metronidazole & 30 µg/ml of Furazolidone

Figure no 6.4.4 (d) chromatogram for linearity concentration-120µg/ml of Metronidazole & 40µg/ml of Furazolidone

Figure no 6.4.4 (e) chromatogram for linearity concentration-150 µg/ml of Metronidazole & 50 µg/ml of Furazolidone

Figure no 6.4.4 (e) chromatogram for linearity concentration-30-150 µg/ml of Metronidazole & 10-50 µg/ml of Furazolidone

Table-6.9 Area of different concentration of Metronidazole and Furazolidone

Concentration $\mu\text{g/ml}$	Metronidazole area	concentration $\mu\text{g/ml}$	Furazolidone area
30	186166	10	30811
60	404720	20	73966
90	593942	30	120415
120	805797	40	166058
150	992321	50	204836

Figure 6.4.4 (f) calibration graph for Furazolidone at 270 nm**Table6.10 Analytical performance parameters of Metronidazole and Furazolidone**

Parameters	Metronidazole	Furazolidone
Slope (m)	6711	4401
Intercept (c)	7426	12825
Correlation coefficient (R^2)	0.999	0.999

Acceptance criteria:

Correlation coefficient (R^2) should not be less than 0.999

The correlation coefficient obtained was 0.999 which is in the acceptance limit. The linearity was established in the range of 10% to 50% of Furazolidone and 30% to 150% of Metronidazole

6.4.5: Limit of detection for Metronidazole and Furazolidone

LOD is calculated based on the standard deviation of the response (SD) and the slope of the calibration curve (S) at levels approximating the LOD according to the formula. The standard deviation of the response can be determined based on the standard deviation of y-intercepts of regression lines.

$$\text{LOD} = 3.3(\text{SD}/S).$$

Where SD = standard deviation

S = slope

Table-6.11 Results of LOD

Drug name	Standard deviation σ	Slope (S)	LOD
Metronidazole	31122.84	6711	4.637
Furazolidone	7833.236	4401	1.7798

6.4.6: Limit of Quantification for Metronidazole and Furazolidone

LOQ calculation is based on the standard deviation of the response (SD) and the slope of the calibration curve (S) according to the formula: Again, the standard deviation of the response can be determined based on the standard deviation of y-intercepts of regression lines.

$$LOQ = 10(SD/S)$$

Where SD = standard deviation

S = slope

Table no-6.12 Results of LOQ

Drug name	Standard deviation σ	Slope (S)	LOQ
Metronidazole	94311	6711	14.053
Furazolidone	23737	4401	5.3935

6.4.7: ROBUSTNESS:

The standard and samples of Metronidazole and Furazolidone were injected by changing the conditions of chromatography. There was no significant change in the parameters like resolution, tailing factor, asymmetric factor, and plate count.

6.4.7.1: Variation in flow**Figure no 6.4.7.1 (b) chromatogram showing more flow of 1.1ml/min****Table-6.13 Results for variation in flow for Metronidazole**

S.No	Flow rate (ml/min)	Area	RT	USP resolution	USP tailing	USP plate count
1	0.9	652984	3.784		1.59	1628
2	1	791096	3.440		1.6	2329
3	1.1	532023	3.106		1.63	1257
Mean		1976103				
Std Dev		129631.1				
%RSD		0.065599				

Table-6.14 Results for variation in flow for Furazolidone

S.No	Flow rate (ml/min)	Area	RT	USP resolution	USP tailing	USP plate count
1	0.9	138572	4.520	1.93	1.55	1472
2	1	115578	4.136	2.2	1.5	2830
3	1.1	113117	3.711	1.76	1.54	1209
Mean		367267				
Std Dev		14040.05				
%RSD		0.038228				

6.4.7.2 Variation of mobile phase organic composition:**Figure no 6.4.7.2 (b) chromatogram showing more organic composition****Table-6.15 Results for variation in mobile phase composition Metronidazole**

S.No	Organic nature	Area	RT	USP resolution	USP tailing	USP plate count
1	Less organic	542114	3.236		1.92	3054
2	optimised	791096	3.440		1.6	2329
3	More organic	527110	2.982		1.74	964
mean		1860320				
Std Dev		148271				
%RSD		0.0797				

Table-6.16 Results for variation in mobile phase composition Furazolidone

S.No	Organic nature	Area	RT	USP resolution	USP tailing	USP plate count
1	Less organic	114331	4.089	2.98	1.92	3909
2	Optimized	115578	4.136	2.2	1.5	2830
3	More organic	114688	3.398	1.22		801
Mean		344597				
Std Dev		642.2043				
%RSD		0.001864				

Acceptance criteria:

Percentage RSD should be below 2.

The %RSD obtained for change of flow rate, variation in mobile phase was found to be below 1, which is within the acceptance criteria. Hence the method is robust.

6.4.8 Specificity**6.4.8a Chromatogram of Blank**

S.No	name	RT	Area	height	USP resolution	USP tailing	USP plate count
1	Metronidazole	3.440	791096	76796		1.6	2329
2	Furazolidone	4.136	115578	10468	2.2	1.5	2830

Observation : The specificity test was performed for Metronidazole and Furazolidone. It was found that there was no interference of impurities in retention time of analytical peak.

6.5 STABILITY STUDIES**6.5.1 Acid degradation:****Figure no 6.5.1a chromatogram showing acid degradation**

S.No	Name	RT	Area	Height (μV)	USP resolution	USP tailing	USP plate count
1	Metronidazole	3.423	721637.8	61936		1.05	2311
2	Furazolidone	4.037	103349.8	29304	2.01	1.02	2317

Observation: acid degradation was found with metronidazole and furazolidone was found to be within the limits.

Fig 6.5.1b Purity peaks for Acid degradation

6.5.2 Base degradation

Figure no 6.5.2a chromatogram showing base degradation

S.No	Name	RT	Area	Height (μV)	USP resolution	USP tailing	USP plate count
1	Metronidazole	3.426	571487	45745		1.07	2207
2	Furazolidone	4.042	88070.44	2053	2.06	1.04	2385

Observation: very high amount of degradation was found with base and impurities were detected.

Fig 6.5.2b Purity peaks for base degradation

6.5.3.Peroxide:

Figure no 6.5.3a chromatogram showing degradation in peroxide

S.No	Name	RT	Area	Height (μV)	USP resolution	USP tailing	USP plate count
1	Metronidazole	3.429	684456	56928		1.04	2135
2	Furazolidone	4.047	100830	46299	1.99	1.01	2153

Observation: Degradation was found to be within the limits. An impurity was found at 2.9 retention.

6.5.3b Purity peaks for oxidation

6.5.4 Thermal degradation:**Figure no 6.5.4a chromatogram showing thermal degradation**

S.No	Name	RT	Area	Height (μV)	USP resolution	USP tailing	USP plate count
1	Metronidazole	3.428	754863	43002		1.11	3463
2	Furazolidone	4.047	106736	12992	2.41	1.10	3802

Observation: degradation was found to be within the limits for thermal degradation. An impurity was detected before metronidazole.

Fig 6.5.4b purity peaks for thermal stability**Figure no 6.5.5a chromatogram showing photostability**

S.No	Name	RT	Area	Height (μV)	USP resolution	USP tailing	USP plate count
1	Metronidazole	3.433	732871	54540		1.06	2615
2	Furazolidone	4.056	109244	27640	2.12	1.04	2685

Observation: degradation was found to be within the limits when the drug was subjected to photo stability testing.

Fig 6.5.5b purity peaks for photo stability

$$\text{Assay \%} = \frac{\text{At} \times \text{Ws} \times \text{P} \times (100 - \text{WC of std})}{\text{As} \times \text{Wt} \times (100 - \text{WC of sample})}$$

At = Area due to sample Preparation
 As = Area due to working standard solution
 Wt = Weight of the sample in mg
 Ws = Weight of the working standard
 P = Potency or Assay of the standard
 WC = % water content of the sample or standard

Table 6.17 Stability Studies

S.no	Type of degradation	Area of sample		Assay content %w/w	
		Metronidazole	Furazolidone	Metronidazole	Furazolidone
1	Acid (0.1N)	721637.8	103349	91.2243	89.4251
2	Base (0.1N)	571487.6	88070.44	72.2456	76.534
3	Peroxide (H ₂ O ₂)	684456.3	100830.2	86.5253	87.2451
4	Thermal	754863.8	106736.3	95.4256	92.3566
5	Photo-stability	732871	109244.3	92.6452	94.3564

7. SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION:

- High performance liquid chromatography is at present one of the most sophisticated tool of the analysis. Furazolidone and Metronidazole combination drug was selected by conforming that the present study was not performed on this combination by thorough literature survey. The estimation of Furazolidone and Metronidazole was done by RP-HPLC.
- The optimized conditions were found to be C₁₈ column C8 (4.6 x 250mm, 5µm, Make: XTerra) as stationary phase, phosphate: acetonitrile: methanol as mobile

phase, 2.5 pH of the phosphate buffer, Wavelength of 270 nm, Ambient temperature, Run time of 8mins. The detection was carried out using PDA detector. The solutions were chromatographed at a constant flow rate of 0.8 ml/min.

- The linearity range of Furazolidone and Metronidazole were found to be from 10-50 µg/ml. and 30-150µg/ml respectively. Linear regression coefficient was not more than 0.999.
- The values of % RSD are less than 2% indicating accuracy and precision of the

method. The percentage recovery varies from 98-102% of Furazolidone and Metronidazole. LOD and LOQ were found to be within limit.

- The results obtained on the validation parameters met ICH and USP requirements. It inferred that the method is simple, accurate, precise and linear. It passes the stability studies with an exception for base stability. The method was found to be have suitable application in routine laboratory analysis with high degree of accuracy and precision.

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